

India's Role in UN Peacekeeping in the Democratic Republic of Congo

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Abstract:

Aftermath the signing of the Lusaka Peace Accord in July 1997, the civil war in the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC) and the neighbouring countries turned into a more serious dimension. Former allies of Laurent Kabila turned against him. President Laurent Kabila was assassinated in January 2001. His son Joseph Kabila succeeded and the succession brought hopes for positive changes. However, the war was drawn into full scale war: Africa's Second World War. The United Nations started sending observers followed by peacekeepers. India sent police personnel, military experts and troops numbering 7072 by March 2015 out of a world total of 10654. Indian peacekeepers were mostly concentrated in the storm centres of intense fighting. The following article is an evaluation of Indian peacekeepers in the DRC.)

Laurent Kabila of the ADFL¹ overthrew Mobutu Sese Seko's 32-year old dictatorial rule in May 1997. After Kabila's victory, Kabila's former allies turned against him and inaugurated Africa's deadliest war which fought for five years and left 5.4 million dead from war, disease and starvation. It is also seen the wide scale displacement of 3.4 million people. While the

¹ **ADFL/AFDL/ADFLC** - *Alliance des Forces Démocratiques pour la Libération du Congo-Zaire* (The Alliance of Democratic Forces for the Liberation of Congo-Zaire - ADFL or AFDL or ADFLC) was a coalition of Congolese dissidents, disgruntled minority groups and nations especially Rwanda, Uganda and Burundi that toppled President Mobutu Sese Seko and brought Laurent Kabila to power in the First Congo War (1996-1997). While the group was successful in overthrowing the Mobutu dictatorship, the alliance fell apart after Kabila and his Ugandan and Rwandan backers turned on each other, marking the beginning of the Second Congo War 2 on August 1998.

war took into this dimension what was the role of the United Nations in the maintenance of peace and security of the people in the area?

The United Nations took serious note of what was going on in Zaire, later on named as Democratic Republic of Congo. Its Security Council from the very beginning of the war took timely action. For instance, on 9 April 1999, the Security Council called for the immediate signing of a ceasefire agreement. It found the basis to act more actively when the Lusaka Ceasefire Agreement was signed. After its signing the Security Council welcomed the Ceasefire Agreement and authorized on 6 August 1999 the deployment of 50 UN liaison personnel distributing over the capitals of all the warring countries as a significant step. However, despite the signing of the Lusaka Peace Accord, the war turned into a more serious dimension. The Security Council on 24 February 2000 with the resolution 1291, the UN Security Council authorized the deployment of a maximum of 5537 military personnel in the DRC, including 500 military observers. On 4 April 2000 the Senegalese Major General Mountago Diallo was appointed as the commander of MONUC's military force. In substance the mandate was to:

- (i) monitor the implementation of the Ceasefire Agreement and the redeployment of belligerent forces;
- (ii) develop an action plan for the overall implementation of the Ceasefire Agreement
- (iii) work with the parties to obtain the release of all prisoners of war, military captives and the return of the remains;
- (iv) facilitate humanitarian assistance; and
- (v) assist the Facilitator of the National Dialogue.²

Acting under Chapter VII of the United Nations Charter the UN Security Council authorized MONUC³ to take the necessary action, in the areas of deployment of its infantry battalions, to

² <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/MONUSCO#2000>, accessed 04 April 2015.

³ United Nations Organization Mission in the Democratic Republic of Congo

protect UN personnel, facilities, installations and equipment, ensure the security and freedom of movement of its personnel, and to protect civilians under imminent threat of physical violence.

In December 2000 there were 224 military personnel deployed, including 148 observers in 13 points around the country. The observers could only record the non-application of the Ceasefire, the violent fighting at Kisangani and in the Equateur and Katanga provinces as well as the presence of foreign troops in the DRC. The deployment of UN troops was impossible due to the security situation and the reluctance of the Congolese government. However, after the assassination of President Laurent Kabila in January 2001 and his son's succession brought new hopes for positive changes owing to the steps he had taken in line with what was specifically mentioned in the Lusaka Peace Agreement.

In March 2001, the first Uruguayan guard unit arrived in Kalemie. The force was deployed in four sectors at Kananga, Kisangani, Kalemie and Mbandaka. In July 2001, the force strength was of 2366 soldiers, including 363 military observers distributed in 22 cities and 28 teams monitoring the disengagement of forces. The number of soldiers of the contingent came to 1869. They came from South Africa, Uruguay, Morocco, Senegal and Tunisia; protected MONUC installations in Kinshasa, Kananga, Kisangani, Kalemie, Goma and Mbandaka. A Uruguayan riverine unit and a South African air medical evacuation team were also deployed. The deployed troops were only to protect the sites against looting and theft. They did not have the mandate to protect the civilian population, or even to extract MONUC personnel. Following the Security Council Resolution 1355 of 15 June 2001, the military observers, within their capacities, could also contribute to the voluntary disarmament, demobilization, repatriation and reintegration process of the armed groups, popularly known as DDRR later on.

With Security Council Resolution 1376 of 9 November 2001, it launched the third phase of the deployment of MONUC troops, in the east of DRC based at Kindu, the site for the logistical base also.

In 2002, the 450 military observers, split in 95 teams, continued to monitor the Ceasefire along the eastern DRC's international borders. The teams also investigated violations of the Ceasefire. Foreign troops continued to leave the country.⁴ The riverine units escorted the first ships on the Congo River, which was again open to commercial traffic. In June 2002 the blue helmets' total number was 3804. Contingents from Ghana and Bolivia joined the force, of which a third of the soldiers were Uruguayans. More than a thousand soldiers were deployed in Kisangani.

On 30 of July 2002, the different parties signed the Pretoria agreement. With the signing of this agreement the nature of the mission of the peacekeepers changed. The military observers monitored the withdrawal of 20 000 Rwandan soldiers, but they also noted the rise of ethnic violence in Ituri. At the end of 2002 there were a total of 4200 UN soldiers in the DRC. By Resolution 1445 of 4 December 2002 the Security Council authorized the increase of military personnel to 8500. The principle of two independent intervention forces was also approved. MONUC had to support the voluntary disarmament, demobilization, repatriation, reintegration and resettlement (DDRRR) process, but without using force.

Numerous DDRRR operations in collaboration with the civilian component were conducted in the beginning of 2003. Before the start of the transition, UN soldiers were deployed along the front lines. A vast redeployment to the East started. The four coordination centres and 22 bases in the western part of the country were shut down. Over a hundred observers were redeployed and Uruguayan contingents arrived in Bukavu and Lubero. Observer teams monitored serious combat and human rights violations in Ituri.⁵ In April 2003, 800 Uruguayan soldiers were deployed in Bunia under Resolution 1484 of 30 May 2003. In April an observer died in a mine explosion. In May 2003 two military observers were savagely killed by a militia.

However, the withdrawal of 7000 Ugandan troops in April 2003 resulted in the deterioration of security situation in the Ituri region endangering the peace process. The UN Secretary

⁴ <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/MONUSCO#2000>, accessed 04 April 2015.

⁵ en.wikipedia.org/wiki/ituri-conflict, accessed 08 June 2015.

General Kofi Annan called for establishing and deploying a temporary multi-national force to the area until the weakened MONUC mission could be reinforced. In his second special report to the Security Council, the UN Secretary General proposed a reorientation of MONUC missions: to provide support to the transition and to maintain security in key areas of the country. Accordingly he proposed the creation of a brigade in Ituri to support the peace process.

On 30 May 2003, the Security Council by its Resolution 1493 of 28 July 2003 authorized the deployment of interim emergency multinational force in Bunia with a task to secure the airport, protect internally displaced persons in camps and the civilians in the town. The same resolution authorized an increase of military personnel to 10,800 imposed and arms embargo and authorized MONUC to use all necessary means to fulfill its mandate in the Ituri district and, as it deemed it to be within its capabilities, also in North and South Kivu.

Meanwhile considering the seriousness of the conflict, an European Union (EU) led mission in which main bulk of troops were provided by the government of France, also, provided air force. The same force was also added by 80 Swedish troops. The other troop contributors were Belgium, Canada, UK and South Africa and Senegal.⁶ This EU led contingent launched the operation called Operation Artemis on 12 June 2003. The force was successful in stabilising the situation in Bunia and enforcing the UN presence in the DRC. In September 2003, responsibility for the security of the region was handed over to the MONUC mission.

When the conflict in the region became intense, the United Nations decided to seek additional military help from major powers. In response to the call in July 2003, India sent a contingent consisting of approximately 340 personnel from the Air Force and Army led by Group Captain K.S.Gill. They were deployed in the eastern DRC.⁷ In September 2003, the Ituri brigade was in place, including soldiers from Uruguay, Bangladesh, Nepal, Pakistan, Indonesia, India and Morocco. In November 2003, a total of 10,415 peacekeepers were in the DRC, comprising units of infantry, engineers, helicopters, logistic, medical and riverine ones.

⁶ Keesing's Record of World Events, News Digest for June, 2003(London), p.45449.

⁷ Ministry of External Affairs, Government of India, Annual Report, 2003-04, (New Delhi) hereinafter referred to as MEA Report, p 67.

They improved the security conditions. However, at the same time they became targets of the militias too. Even a military observer was killed in Ituri on 12 February 2004.⁸

With the arrival of the Transitional Government of the Democratic Republic of Congo which included members of rebel movements, more than 900 Tunisian and Ghanaian blue helmets contributed to the security of Kinshasa. It was decided that the troops present in the Kivus will be assembled under the unified command of a brigade. In March the Nigerian General Samaila Iliya took over the command of the force. In June 2004, Bukavu was occupied by rebel general Laurent Nkunda. A military observer was killed. The 1000 MONUC troops could only protect their own installations. Demonstrations were held all over the country, forcing blue helmets to open fire on looters in Kinshasa. MONUC soldiers were again targeted by Ituri militia at the end of 2004.

By this time, the Secretary General had asked for an increase of 13,100 soldiers. In October 2004 the Security Council by Resolution 1565, authorized a reinforcement of 5,900 military personnel and defines the mandate which is still valid today. The strategic military objectives of the MONUC force were:

- proactively contributing to the pacification and general improvement of security in the country;
- providing support for conflict resolution in politically volatile areas;
- improving border security through regional confidence-building mechanisms, such as the Joint Verification Mechanism, and effective patrolling and monitoring of the arms embargo;
- gathering and analysing military and other information on spoilers.

Following the UN resolution, the Indian Army announced that it would be sending an additional 850 troops and four combat helicopters to aid the MONUC peacekeeping effort.⁹

⁸ <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/MONUSCO#2000>, accessed 04 April 2015.

By 2005, the strength of UN peacekeeping forces in Congo reached more than 16,000 troops, split almost equally between the Western Brigade and the Eastern Division.

One of the most important imperatives to increase the strength of the peacekeepers was that the militia targeted the UN peacekeepers. In February 2005, 9 Bangladeshi peacekeepers were killed in an ambush in Ituri. International peacekeeping in the area became risky. Consequence upon the ambush Thomas Lubanga Dyilo, the leader of the Union of Congolese Patriots, The Union of Congolese Patriots (French: *Union des Patriotes Congolais*, UPC is a political and militia group in Ituri, northeastern Democratic Republic of the Congo, formed towards the end of the Second Congo War. It was founded by Thomas Lubanga in 2001, and was one of six such groups that sprung up in the mineral-rich Ituri region on the border with Uganda in the Ituri conflict. The UPC was primarily composed of the Hema ethnic group. By February 2003, the UPC was said to have fielded an estimated 15,000 soldiers. It carried out numerous attacks upon civilians and other serious human rights abuses in pursuit of its policies.

In August 2002, the UPC took control of the town of Bunia with the help of Ugandan forces, following which it received support from Rwanda. In late 2003, the UPC split into several factions: one led by Kisembo Bahemuka and known as the UPC-Kisembo (UPC-K), another under Thomas Lubanga and known as the UPC-Lubanga (UPC-L), and the *Parti pour l'unité et la sauvegarde de l'intégrité du Congo* (PUSIC) - Party for Unity and Safeguarding of the Integrity of Congo, formed by Mandro Panga Kahwa. The UPC-L was militarily stronger as most of the militia stayed with Lubanga. After the 2004 accords most of the UPC-K eventually merged into PUSIC.

The UPC-L was implicated in the deaths of nine Bangladeshi MONUC peacekeepers on 25 March 2005. Lubanga was arrested along with Floribert Ndjabu, leader of the Nationalist and Integrationist Front. In March 2006, Lubanga was arrested under a warrant issued by the International Criminal Court for the alleged war crime of using child soldiers, and was flown to the Netherlands.

⁹ “DRC: India, Pakistan to send More troops”, at <http://www.irinnews.org/report/51595/drc-india-pakistan-to-send-more-troops> , accessed 11 June 2011.

Bosco Ntaganda was named its leader in his absence. Human Rights Watch stated that between August 2002 and March 2003, the UPC arrested and tortured over 100 opponents, was responsible for the murder of a Kenyan peacekeeper in January 2004 and the kidnapping of a Moroccan peacekeeper later that year. In January 2005, Commander Bosco Ntaganda was offered a position as a general in the national *Forces Armées de la République Démocratique du Congo* (FARDC), but had refused the post.

The UPC won three National Assembly seats in the 2006 general elections¹⁰ and other militia leaders were arrested by Congolese authorities and imprisoned in Makala, Kinshasa. Lubanga was accused of having ordered the killing of the peacekeepers in February 2005 and charged for “conscripting and enlisting children under the age of fifteen years and using them to participate actively in hostilities”. The Congolese national authorities transferred Lubanga to ICC custody on 17 March 2006.¹¹ Following the killing of those Bangladeshi soldiers a vast cordon and search operation in Ituri was conducted on 1 March 2005 by Nepalese, Pakistani and South African Infantry elements with the support of Indian attack helicopters. Between 50 and 60 militiamen were killed.

In October 2005, by Resolution 1635 of 28 October 2005, the UN Security Council authorized a temporary increase of 300 military personnel to permit a deployment to Katanga.¹²

Another UNSC resolution, UNSC Resolution 1671 of 25 April 2006 authorised temporary deployment of a European Union force to support MONUC during the period encompassing the general elections in the DR Congo, which began on 30 July 2006.

Meanwhile, the European Council approved the launching of the EU military operation, EUFOR RD Congo, and appointed Lieutenant General Karlheinz Viereck (Germany)

¹⁰ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Union_of_Congolese_Patriots, accessed 14 June 2015

¹¹ “DR Congo rebel faces Hague trial”, <http://news.bbc.co.uk/2/hi/africa/4815966.stm>, 17 March 2006, accessed 15 June 2015

¹² <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/MONUSCO#2000>, accessed 04 April 2015.

Operation Commander and Major General Christian Damay (France) EU Force Commander. The operation was tasked with:

- supporting and providing security to MONUC installations and personnel;
- contributing to airport protection in Kinshasa;
- contributing to the protection of civilians under imminent threat of physical violence;
- evacuation operations in case of emergency

This mission came to an end on 30 November 2006.¹³ In May 2007, India announced to send an additional 70 Indian Air Force personnel to join the MONUC effort of which details are discussed below.

On 26 October 2008 Rally for Congolese Democracy (RCD) forces of Laurent Nkunda seized a major military camp, along with Virunga National Park for use as a base to launch attacks. This occurred after a peace treaty failed, with the resultant fighting displacing thousands.¹⁴ The park was taken due to its strategic location on a main road leading to the city of Goma.

On 27 October 2008 riots began around the United Nations compound in Goma, and civilians pelted the building with rocks and threw Molotov cocktails, claiming that the UN forces had done nothing to prevent the RCD advance.¹⁵ The Congolese national army also retreated under pressure from the rebel army in a “major retreat”. A pitched battle was fought with United Nations gunships and armoured vehicles were used in an effort to halt the advance of the rebels, who were only 7 miles away from Goma. Special Representative of the UN Secretary-General for DRC Alan Doss explained the necessity of engaging the rebels, stating that “... [the UN] can’t allow population centres to be threatened... [the UN] had to engage”.¹⁶

¹³ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/EUFOR_DR_Congo, accessed 14 June 2015.

¹⁴ <http://edition.cnn.com/2008/WORLD/africa/10/26/congo.gorillapark/index.html?eref=onion>, accessed 15 June 2015.

¹⁵ CNN (2008), “Protesters attack U.N.HQ in eastern Congo”, *CNN*, United States, 26 October 2008.

¹⁶ BBC News (2008), “UN joins battle with Congo rebels” BBC News, *London*, 27 October 2008.

Indian and Uruguayan forces played a key and significant role in this campaign. In November, India made another announcement for reinforcement by sending 3rd battalion of the elite 3rd Gurkha Regiment to join the peace-keeping effort in Congo¹⁷ as it was concerned about the militia attack on Indian peacekeepers.¹⁸ In the meantime Britain, France, backed by 44 different organisations pressurised the UN Security Council to send 3000 troops more to the DRC strife torn areas.¹⁹ A similar view also was expressed by Human Rights Watch and other humanitarian aid groups in the region. The intense fighting caused untold miseries in the form of deaths, rapes, lootings, forced recruitment and further displacements of civilian populations. Fighting also tore apart the region of Rutshuru, particularly the town of Kiwanja, where hundreds of civilian deaths were now recorded. Local groups in the Congo also requested help from the European Union, as they would be able to deploy soldiers sooner; working as a “bridging force” until the UN reinforcements arrived.²⁰

On 20 November, the UN voted unanimously to send 3,085 more peacekeepers, citing “extreme concern at the deteriorating humanitarian situation and in particular the targeted attacks against civilian population, sexual violence, recruitment of child soldiers and summary executions”. However, it did not extend MONUC’s mandate in the Congo, which expired at the end of 2008.²¹ The decision was made despite the rebel commitment to pulling back from the front lines and allowing aid to reach the thousands of people still isolated, according to aid groups.

¹⁷ Majumdar, Bappa (2008), “Gurkhas to join Indian troops in Congo U.N. force”, *Reuters*, [Online: web] 7 November, Accessed 28 November 2013, URL: <http://in.reuters.com/article/2008/11/07/idINIndia-36382420081107>.

¹⁸Ibid.

¹⁹CNN (2008), “Britain, France push for more U.N. troops in Congo”, *CNN*, United States, 20 Nov 2008.

²⁰Ibid.

²¹CNN (2008), “U.N. condemns Congo atrocities”, *CNN*, United States, 20 November 2008.

However, a week after the UN vote, the DRC government requested the UN not to deploy any more Indian troops in the east of the country, arguing that there was a need to “redress the balance” of the make-up of the 17,000-strong UN force in the country.²²

On 17 February, Egypt announced that it would send around 1,325 soldiers from the Egyptian Army to support the UN mission in Congo. Egypt also announced that it would send a police force to help in protecting the UN mission in Congo. The Egyptian armed force was supposed to work to give support and technical advice to the Congo Army besides operating armed mission in the conflict zones and medical assistance and support. According to the Foreign affairs in Cairo, Egypt assured to send a Mechanized Unit, Special Forces, Field Engineers, and Paratroops. Egypt already had a small unit in Congo consisting of 13 policemen and 23 observers.²³

Meanwhile in March 2009, the Indian Army questioned more than 100 Indian troops deployed in DRC regarding the allegations against them. After a thorough investigation, which included examination of statements by alleged victims, the Indian Army found “serious irregularities” in charges raised by the United Nations Office of Internal Oversight Services. Consequently, all of the accused personnel were let off due to lack of evidence.²⁴

In December, MONUC rushed peacekeeping troops to Dongo in the Kungu territory of Sud-Ubangi District where a new conflict rapidly escalated in an effort to protect the local population. At the weekly MONUC press conference of 16 December 2009, it was announced by MONUC spokesperson Madnodje Mounoubai that the first MONUC peacekeeping troops were deployed in Dongo, where a temporary operational basis was functional, as well as in nearby Bozene. The 500 MONUC troops would come from the Ghanaian, Tunisian and Egyptian contingents as well as troops from the Guatemalan Special

²² BBC News (2008), “DR Congo declines Indian troops”, *BBC News*, London, 26 November 2008.

²³ “Egypt to send more than 1,325 peacekeepers to Congo”, Reuters, 17 February 2009, at <http://af.reuters.com/article/topNews/idAFJOE51H05Q20090218>, accessed 15 June 2015.

²⁴ Indian Express (2009), “Congo abuse: Army clean chit to soldiers” *Indian Express*, New Delhi, 13 March 2009.

Forces. Military equipment such as armoured personnel carriers, transport and combat helicopters would also be at their disposal to support their mission.²⁵

In accordance with Security Council resolution 1925 of 28 May 2010, MONUC was renamed as of 1 July the United Nations Organization Stabilization Mission in the Democratic Republic of the Congo (MONUSCO) inaugurating a new phase in peacekeeping. In August 2010, the Mai Mai rebels ambushed a base of the 19th Kumaon Regiment of the Indian Army, killing three Indian peace-keepers. The attack renewed calls in India to decrease the country's military presence in Congo due to growing conflict in the region.

The UN also withdrew its peacekeepers from a number of fronts in an "orderly, progressive withdrawal" of MONUSCO due to "normalization" of DRC's relations with neighbouring countries and containment of rebels to a "few isolated zones". However conflicts still continued.

In March 2013, the United Nations Security Council authorized the deployment of an intervention brigade within MONUSCO to carry out targeted offensive operations, with or without the Congolese national army, against armed groups that threaten peace in eastern DRC. The brigade was based in Sake, North Kivu and was made up of a total of 3,069 peacekeepers. It was tasked with neutralizing armed groups, reducing the threat posed to State authority and civilian security and to make space for stabilization activities.²⁶ The first Brigade was composed of three battalions, one each from South Africa, Tanzania and Malawi with the Brigade being commanded by Brig-Gen James Makibolwa of Tanzania.

On 30 July 2013, the March 23 Movement was given a 48 hour ultimatum by the UN to leave Goma area or face "use of force".²⁷ Between 21 and 29 August, heavy fighting outside Goma

²⁵ DRC: Equateur: An extra 500 MONUC troops being deployed to Dongo, MONUC at <http://reliefweb.int/report/democratic-republic-congo/dr-congo-equateur-extra-500-monuc-troops-being-deployed-dongo>, accessed 09 June 2015.

²⁶United Nations (2013), "Tanzanian troops arrive in eastern Congo as part of UN intervention brigade", dated 10 May 2013 cited in <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/MONUSCO#2000>, accessed 09 June 2015.

²⁷Al Jazeera (English) (2013), "UN gives ultimatum to DR Congo rebels – Africa", [Online: web] 30 July, Accessed 10 June 2015, URL: <http://www.aljazeera.com/news/africa/2013/07/201373017252298401.html>

left 57 rebels, 10–23 government soldiers, 14 civilians and one Tanzanian UN peacekeeper dead. 720 government soldiers and 10 UN peacekeepers were also wounded.²⁸

After the 2014 South Kivu attack in June 2014, the UN announced it would send MONUSCO peacekeeping troops to the area to protect the population. “These violent acts are unacceptable and need to stop immediately”, said Martin Kobler of Germany, Special Representative for the United Nations Organisation Stabilisation Mission in the Democratic Republic of Congo, MONUSCO.²⁹

3.4: India and the UN Peacekeeping in the DRC

In the above discussion we have seen how the United Nations was gradually drawn to the maintenance of peace and order in the DRC. Towards this end, a large number of troops went to the DRC as peacekeepers. At the same time many countries sent their police personal, military observers. India is not an exception.

India is one of the largest troop contributors in the UN peacekeeping for decades. As on 31 March 2015, the United Nations deployed a total of 1, 06,854 of which there were 91,932 troops, 13,126 police personnel, and 1796 military experts. As on 30 April 2015, India was the third largest contributor of troops with 7072 along with 984 police, and 65 military experts in the DRC totalling 8121.³⁰ See table below:

Table 3.2: Contributors to United Nations Peacekeeping Operations, Monthly Summary of Contributions (Police, UN Military Experts on Mission and Troops), as of 31 March 2015

No.	Country	Police	UNMEM	Troops	Total
1	Bangladesh	1379	77	8060	9516

²⁸Al Jazeera (English) (2013), “UN gives ultimatum to DR Congo rebels – Africa”, [Online: web] 30 July, Accessed 10 June 2015, URL: <http://www.aljazeera.com/news/africa/2013/07/201373017252298401.html>

²⁹ Kyalangalilwa, Crispin (2014), “Dispute over cows leaves 37 dead, 20 others injured in eastern Congo”, Chicago Tribune, Chicago, at http://articles.chicagotribune.com/2014-06-07/news/sns-rt-us-congo-massacre-20140607_1_national-liberation-forces-cows-burundi. Chicago Tribune, accessed 14 June 2015.

³⁰ See also <http://www.un.org/peacekeeping/resources/statistics/contributor.shtml>, accessed 05 May 2015

2	Egypt	444	76	2384	2904
3	Ethopia	39	106	7717	7862
4	India	984	65	7072	8121
5	Nepal	821	56	4367	5244
6	Pakistan	466	89	7794	8349
7	Rwanda	617	27	5065	5709

The above countries along with 114 other countries contributed 13126 police personnel 1796 military experts 91932 troops making a total of 106854

Source: Indian Army's Participation in UN Peacekeeping Missions, Monthly Update at Centre for United Nations Peacekeeping at www.usiofindia.org/cunpk.htm

At one time India was the largest contributor of Peacekeepers in the DRC. Today, as the above table shows Bangladesh with 8060 troops with 1379 police personnel and 77 military experts totalling 9516 is the largest contributor of UN peacekeepers in the DRC. Next comes Pakistan with 7794 troops with 466 police personnel and 89 military experts. Today, 122 countries of the world have contributed peacekeepers in the DRC which has got police personnel, military experts and the troops. The deployment of peacekeepers in the DRC is the largest ever undertaken by the United Nations. Moreover, since 1999 the United Nations has spent about US \$ 8.73 billion to fund the UN peacekeeping.³¹

India's first contingent of peacekeepers to DRC was sent in July 2003. It was an Indian Air Force Helicopter Contingent in the UN Peacekeeping Mission in the Democratic Republic of Congo (MONUC). In a press release issued by the Ministry of External Affairs, Government of India said,

“On 12 July 2003, India sent its Indian Air Force contingent as a part of the U.N. Peacekeeping Mission in the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC) called ‘MONUC’. While sending the contingent, it said, India's decision to send this specialized contingent of over 300 personnel underlines its continuing commitment to the Charter and the principles of the UN and to peacekeeping as an invaluable instrument for the maintenance of international

³¹ <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/MONUSCO>, accessed 05 June 2015.

peace and security. India is one of the longest serving and the largest troop contributors to UN's peacekeeping activities, with more than 65,000 Indian troops, Military Observers and Civilian Police Officers having served in 36 UN peacekeeping missions over the last five decades".³²

India further said that it was in response to a specific request from the U.N. for aerial support to the ground operations of MONUC. According to the release it was the largest that the IAF has ever lent to a UN Mission, the first case where IAF would be providing support to foreign military forces and also the largest Air Force contingent in Congo. The contingent consisted of two helicopter squadrons- (i) Mi-25, (ii) Mi-17. This Air Force contingent was led by Group Captain K.S.Gill. In subsequent years, an officer of the rank of Group Captain commanded the squadrons.³³

The task of the Mi-17 Squadron included troop insertion/extraction, casualty evacuation, disarmament, demobilization and resettlement (DDR) support, logistics supply, search and rescue, observation and reconnaissance. It flew more than 13000 sorties and 8000 flight hours during their operations. These helicopters were also exclusively responsible for the induction and extraction of UN troops. The IAC also assisted various DRC/foreign troops including troops from Pakistan, Bangladesh, South Africa, Uruguay, and Guatemala in their ground operations. On 26 October 2008, One Mi 17 mission of IAC was involved in a daring operation, a Portuguese lady was saved from Rutshuru in the face of heavy enemy firing all around the helipad area without the basic support of ATS services at either of the locations. This act was well appreciated by the Special Representative of the UN Secretary-General of MONUC, Mr. Alan Doss. The squadron was commanded by a successive officers of the rank of Wing Commanders.³⁴

³²Press Release, Ministry of External Affairs, Government of India, dated 8 July 2003, <http://www.mea.gov.in/press-releases.htm?dtl/7895/Deployment+of+Indian+Air+Force+Helicopter+Contingent+in+the+UN+Peacekeeping+Mission+in+the+Democratic+Republic+of+Congo+Monuc>, downloaded on 15 June 2015.

³³ http://indianairforce.nic.in/show_page.php?pg_id=160, accessed, 15 June 2015

³⁴ Source: http://indianairforce.nic.in/show_page.php?pg_id=160, accessed 15 June 2015

The next MI 25 Squadron was instrumental in restoring peace and stability in North Kivu and Ituri regions of DRC. Its manifold task included Armed reconnaissance and surveillance, Fire support to heliborne forces during critical phases of flight and Armed escort to UN aircraft and ground forces. Its operations covered vast inaccessible regions of eastern DRC. During their deployment the unit clocked more than 5000 flight hours.

IAC-I was at the forefront of all the offensive support and humanitarian tasks of MONUC during its deployment. The number of operations undertaken to handle battle hardy rebels exceeded more than 30. The major operations in which the IAC-I took part were: (i) Operation North Nationalism; (ii) Operation North Necktie; (iii) Operation North Nuclide; (iv) Operations Sake; (v) Operations Regular Casevac etc.³⁵ More than 18,000 accident free sorties were flown in the inhospitable terrains of DRC.

Apart from these, when Russian Mi-8 crashed on 18 December 2007 at Rubaya while on a routine mission from Goma to Walikale, the Contingent immediately launched two Mi- 17s for search and rescue of the crashed area. The first helicopter located the crash site, winched up the critical casualties including one dead body. The second one picked up the remaining six personnel in a low hover. The rescue effort was executed in a precise and professional manner. Secondly, the Contingent flew more than 1000 sorties carrying close to 2000 personnel and 1500 tons of load to increase the presence of MONUC troops inside the negative forces controlled area.

Thirdly, Mi-25s flew more than 1000 hrs during Ituri Engraver at Bunia, which was launched to flush out Front for patriotic Resistance in Ituri (FRPI) militias by providing aerial cover to MONUC ground forces. It also played key role in the surrender of their arms from a few rebel FDLR soldiers. Apart from these combat, rescue and reconnaissance activities it also played an important role in social service like distributing books and sports gear to orphans to build up goodwill among the local populace.

³⁵ Press Release, Ministry of External Affairs, Government of India, dated 8 July 2003, <http://www.mea.gov.in/press-releases.htm?dtl/7895/Deployment+of+Indian+Air+Force+Helicopter+Contingent+in+the+UN+Peacekeeping+Mission+in+the+Democratic+Republic+of+Congo+Monuc>, accessed 15 June 2015.

The next Indian contingent arrived in November 2004 and most of them were deployed in North Kivu, the centre of intense fighting which is still continued, of course off and on sporadically.

As already mentioned MONUC peacekeeping contingents were divided into two separate commands in the beginning of 2007:

- (i) The western brigade was stationed in Kinshasa and in the Provinces of Bas Congo, Equateur, Bandundu and
- (ii) The two Kasais

Below is a map of MONUC/MONUSCO troops distribution in the Democratic Republic of Congo. Here we can see that the Indian troops are stationed at the most critical areas.

The main responsibility of the brigade was to protect MONUC installations in Kinshasa. The brigade also had protection elements deployed in Mbandaka, Kananga and Mbuji Mayi.

The eastern division had three brigades located at (i) Ituri, (Four infantry battalions from Bangladesh, Morocco and others); (ii) North Kivu (three battalions from India and others) and; (iii) South Kivu (three battalions from Pakistan, China and others) respectively. Ituri, North and South Kivu are the most sensitive trouble spots in the DRC where warring rebels have taken refuge and fought bloody battles. It had claimed hundreds and thousands of lives including those who died of hunger, diseases and as war casualties along with hundreds and thousands of displaced persons. It also had troops in the provinces of Maniema, Orientale and Katanga. Its UN divisional Headquarters was at Kishangani. Military observers and staff officers from 47 different nations were deployed in the mission. The largest troop contributors for MONUC were Bangladesh, India, Nepal, Pakistan, South Africa and Uruguay (See table below).

Table: Largest troop contributors, MONUC/MONUSCO (as of 31 March 2015)

No	Country	Police	UNMEM	Troops	Total
1.	Bangladesh	1,379	77	8,060	9,516
2.	India	984	65	7,072	8,121
3.	Nepal	821	56	4,367	5,244
4.	Pakistan	466	89	7,794	8,349
5.	South Africa	23	15	2,095	2,133
6.	Uruguay	5	17	1,293	1,315

Source: Indian Army’s Participation in UN peacekeeping Missions, monthly update at Center for United Nations Peacekeeping at www.usiofindia.org/cunpk.htm

Air Force support contingents were there; (i) from Bangladesh and India with detachments located at Goma, Bunia and Bukavu; (ii) Air support units from India and Uruguay in Kindu and Bukavu. Three brigade hospitals were also run one each by China, India and Morocco. Other support element like engineers riverine forces were attached to these brigades.

According to the information provided by Lt Gen Satish Nambiar in his book, “*For the Honour of India: A History of Indian Peacekeeping*”, various Indian battalions were deployed making them a brigade. Successive Brigade commanders were Brigadiers Vikram Puri, G.V Satyanarayana, Pramod Behl and Bipin Rawat of the Indian contingent Brigades from 2004 November to December 2008. 10th Battalion, the Bihar Regiment, 22nd Battalion, the Grenadiers (22 Grenadiers), 3rd Battalion, the Mahar Regiment (3 Mahar), 5th Battalion, the Parachute Regiment 15th Battalion, the Kumaon Regiment 2nd Battalion, the 11th Gorkha Rifles 26th Battalion, the Madras Regiment, 15th Battalion, the Maratha Light Infantry 1st Battalion, the Jammu and Kashmir Rifles 6th Battalion, the Sikh Regiment 5th Battalion, the Garhwal Rifles (5 Garh Rif), 10th Battalion, the Assam Regiment from July 2006 to July 2007: 2nd Battalion, the Rajputana Rifles 6th Battalion, the Sikh Light Infantry were deployed and they were supported by various mechanised, engineer companies while air support was provided by Reconnaissance and Observation Flight, and Level III by the Army Aviation Corps.

The military observers deputed by India to the mission from 2003 were posted at Bunia, in the northeast Ituri Province, and at Goma in North Kivu Province (the most sensitive centres of conflict, see map, p 153). In November 2004, components of 301 Infantry Brigade Group were deployed to North Kivu province, in the north-eastern part of the DRC. North Kivu is the home of various armed groups where the Alliance of Democratic Forces (ADF), made up of rebel Ugandan forces and supported by the Government of Sudan; the Forces for the Democratic Liberation of Rwanda (*Forces du Democratique Liberation du Rwanda* or FDLR) with the Kivu-based Army for the Liberation of Rwanda (*Armee de Liberation Du Rwanda* or ALiR) command; the Mayi-Mayi, a loose association of traditional Congolese local defence forces; Rwandophones, mainly Hutus and Tutsis operated. On the other hand the ill equipped poorly trained the Armed Forces of the DRC, re-christened as *Forces Armées de la Republique Democratique du Congo* (FARDC) were posted in the year 2003. The area was characterised by political instability, civil unrest, and large-scale violation of human rights, deeply disturbed people by these forces, and moreover, populated by a huge number of internally displaced persons. It was the centre of bitter fights for the control of minerals too.

When 301 Infantry Brigade Group, under the command of Brigadier Vikram Puri, was deployed in the mission area, the Military Region had nearly 11 brigades of various nations - the strength of a brigade varying from a few hundred to a few thousand. On 17 January 2005, 301 Infantry Brigade Group formally took over responsibility for North Kivu. The main tasks given to the Brigade were to: (i) promote confidence among the people by its presence in North Kivu Province; (ii) obstruct or undermine conflict settlement through violent means with a threat to peace process; (iii) ensure security and freedom of movement of UN personnel and protect of UN facilities; (iv) to protect humanitarian aid groups; and finally, (v) to monitor the arms embargo by instituting checks at border crossings.

The presence of UN troops in all the major population centres considerably facilitated the return of locals who had been displaced due to the November 2004 crisis.

Operational Activities of 301 Infantry Brigade Group

The operational activities of 301 Brigade Group included first, creation of an environment conducive for the holding of elections and their actual administration. Secondly, another important process that was required was to demobilise soldiers and fighters to be retrained for 45 days and then to be redeployed in a region other than the one in which they had earlier fought. Under the active and calculated initiative these two main activities were successfully carried out under the leadership of Brigadier Vikram Puri, Commander 301 Brigade Group and Brigadier General Gabriel Amisi, Commander of the 8th Military Region. Both the military officers were largely responsible for doing away with the mono ethnic characteristics of the militias.³⁶ The author already acknowledges the help rendered by the Centre of United Nations Peacekeeping (CUNPK), New Delhi in the compilation of these facts. Moreover, for these operations, the author has taken out most of the write up of Lt. Gen Satish Nambiar, “For the Honour of India: A History of the Indian Peacekeeping”.

³⁶ Press Release, Ministry of External Affairs, Government of India, dated 8 July 2003, <http://www.mea.gov.in/press-releases.htm?dtl/7895/Deployment+of+Indian+Air+Force+Helicopter+Contingent+in+the+UN+Peacekeeping+Mission+in+the+Democratic+Republic+of+Congo+Monuc>, accessed 15 June 2015.

Regarding the second activity, it was well executed. More than 10,000 fighters of various militia groups were peacefully concentrated at the two centres within the province. 8,000 weapons were collected from the groups and secured under UN auspices. Personnel from various other factions of the FARDC volunteered to re-integrate and were marshalled, disarmed, integrated and re-trained. Their training programme included basic tactics and use of weapons, leadership, practice in field conditions, military discipline and democracy, physical training and education on international human rights laws. They were also trained for offensive and defensive operations, and to provide support to peace operations.

The 301 Indian contingents Brigade also launched more than a dozen tough challenging operations;

- (i) Operation Kavach; The first operation known as the Operation Kavach was launched on 26 February 2005 at Kamango, basically to resolve humanitarian crisis created by a militia group belonging to ADF/NALU (National Army for the Liberation of Uganda which targeted local civilians killing and creating chaos. The humanitarian crisis was resolved and further escalation avoided.³⁷
- (ii) Operation Reach-Out; The second operation Operation Reach-Out, was launched Karuruma from 6-8 May 2005 ‘to dominate’ the area and win the confidence of the people in far flung inaccessible villages of North Kivu province.
- (iii) Operation Growing Lion; Third operation, Growing Lion was launched in 8 August 2005 at Katoyi and Mutongo areas. To undertake a meaningful dialogue with foreign armed groups and was successful in establishing MONUC forces in the area. Of course, it has strong support of the villagers.
- (iv) Operation Restore Harmony and Operation Taming Turncoats in August 2005 were launched by 10 BR Regiment. The basic objective of the operations was for disarmament and the reintegration of the 12th DRC brigade soldiers who had

³⁷ Ibid.

deserted their units and wanted to join the militia led by General Laurent Nkunda. In all 569 soldiers along with 497 weapons were surrendered.

- (v) Operation North Nexus was launched on 31 October 2005. It was to clear Virunga National Park - national heritage site of the DRC - located in North Kivu bordering Rwanda and Uganda, of rebel militias, such as the FDLR and the Jackson Mayi-Mayi, who were using it as a hide-out. UN forces advanced. A total of seven militia camps were destroyed, 304 militia personnel with 152 weapons were apprehended or forced to surrender, and the area was cleared of all armed groups. To stabilise conditions in the areas secured, FARDC troops were redeployed.
- (vi) Operation North Niece was launched on 31 October 2005 jointly by the troops of the Indian Brigade and the FARDC to rescue kidnapped officials of the Election Commission. Fierce fighting took place in North Kivu. The Joint effort successfully freed the kidnapped electoral personnel. This was the first joint operation in which Indian Air Force helicopters were deployed.
- (vii) Operation North Night Finale was launched from 23 to 27 December 2005 against Allied Democratic Forces (ADF) rebels in Grand North to destroy the ADF strongholds in the area. Swift operations were conducted by 22 Grenadiers and FARDC troops supported by IAF attack helicopters killed 99 ADF cadres and captured two cadres during the operations.
- (viii) Operation North Necklace was a joint operation conducted by 5 Para and FARDC forces from 12 to 18 April 2006. A major FDLR camp in Virunga National Park (West) was destroyed, and 17 FDLR fighters were killed and three captured. A large cache of arms and ammunition was recovered. Operation North Network launched in May 2006 was a similar joint operation undertaken to clear the eastern portion of the Virunga National Park near Katweguru. The FDLR stronghold was destroyed, and 11 FDLR operatives were killed. During the

subsequent rotation, an additional Indian battalion – 2 Raj Rif - was inducted. It deployed in Katanga, and was part of the Katanga Brigade.

- (ix) Operation Rising Sun was connected with Conduct of Elections in the DRC. In July 2006 the presidential and legislative elections finally took place. To ensure that the election process was carried out peacefully, Operation Rising Sun was undertaken by the North Kivu Brigade to support the electoral process in the province and to prevent any disruptions. A total of 1,522 Indian contingent patrol parties were tasked for the purpose. In performing this task, they covered over 9,110 kilometres, including 3,110 kilometres solely on foot. Special armed escorts were provided to the parties transporting election materials such as ballot boxes, ballot papers, and booths to designated distribution sites that were required to take electoral material to designated polling booths. During the polling phase from 26 October to 1 November 2006, when the elections actually took place, 301 Brigade Group undertook a 28-point deployment, the most extensive deployment by any MONUC Brigade for the elections.
- (x) Securing Goma Operation was another operation launched in response a major politico-military crisis developed in North Kivu Province when a prominent member of the Tutsi community was killed by the Provincial Police over an altercation at a police barrier in Sake on 24 November 2006, (27 kilometres East of Goma) aftermath of the declaration of the election results. The incident provoked General Nkunda to attack the FARDC Integrated Brigades at Sake. 301 Indian anticipated that their forces might attack Goma, the capital of the North Kivu Province, a centre of political, military instability in Eastern Congo. It was also the HQ of MONUC forces in the province and local offices of a number of international aid agencies quite close to Rwanda (a Tutsi ruled state). Any serious threat to this strategically important town had far-reaching implications, and directly challenged the effectiveness of the strong military presence the UN had in the region. The 301 Brigade Group reacted swiftly the town. Indian forces that included 5 Para, 2/11 GR and 15 Kumaon saved the situation in Goma and Sake.

(xi) Operation Safe Hands was another significant operation which was conducted from 24 October 2006 to January 2007, during which time over 600 illegal weapons were recovered. In another significant operation the Indian peacekeepers repulsed General Nkunda's forces when they made an attempt to Sake, an important communication centre. In addition to the above operations, Indian Air Force helicopter squadrons showed exemplary service in the identification and spotting rebel militant camps, transfer of troops on important missions on various occasions. In substance Mi-17 helicopters completed 4000 flying hours in over 6000 sorties. In the Indian Air Force in MONUC Phase II their helicopters were put into service where Indian or joint operations were conducted. They performed dual role supporting operations in North Kivu and Ituri Brigades in supporting civilian infrastructure of MONUC.

(xii) Sake Crisis

In September 2007, the rebels attacked and captured nearby Ridge top and attempted to proceed towards Sake town. Sake Town is an important communication centre, which the Nkunda forces had repeatedly tried to capture which had been dealt with somewhat in detail elsewhere in this chapter. Over the next few months, from September to December 2007, the Government tried to negotiate with General Nkunda to integrate his troops in the national army as the government was ready. To assist in the peace process, The Indian contingent 1 JAK Rifles set up two reception centres for rebel troops at Mushake and Kilolirwe by establishing mobile operating bases. However, no agreement could be reached and fighting broke out at various places again. During the process, on 9 December 2007, Nkunda's troops attacked Sake, and within 48 hours were able to reclaim most of the territory in its vicinity. The Indian forces supported the government troops in retaliating against General Nkunda's forces, and by 15 December 2007 the rebels were forced to withdraw to Celtel Ridge top again.

While the Indian peacekeepers taking up the above military campaigns and peace initiatives, it is worthwhile to record the contributions made by the Indian Air Force in critical situations which are discussed earlier.

To add a few lines, the General writes, IAF Squadron 2006 - the utility helicopter component- with Mi-17s, was based at Bukavu and IAF Squadron 2005 with the upgraded Mi-35s was positioned at Goma, near the Brigade Headquarters. The Mi-35s were part of the attack helicopter component. In late 2005, the IAF contingent conducted operations against the FDLR and Mayi-Mayi cadres in Virunga National Park and the Lusamambo areas in support of 301 Brigade Group. The Mi-35s operating outside Bunia were used against militia forces of Peter Karim, a local warlord in the Fataki area. Mi-17 helicopters of the IAF contingent were involved in almost all the operations launched by 301 Brigade Group, for casualty evacuation as well as for insertion and extraction of troops. They performed very effectively during operations North Nexus, North Night Finale and North Nimble in North Kivu province.

During the referendum on the Constitution, IAF Mi-17s were deployed to make sure that election materials and polling staff reached remote and inaccessible polling stations.

The Mi-35 helicopters provided close support to the ground forces by engaging hostile targets and transporting personnel and cargo. Their missions were armed reconnaissance and surveillance, fire support to helicopter-borne forces during critical phases of flight, armed escort to the UN air contingent and armed escort to ground forces. They also provided aerial cover during the insertion or extraction of troops and UN civilians.

In MONUC, the Indian Air Force Contingent fulfilled a dual role – a military one of supporting operations of the UN North Kivu and Ituri Brigades and a non-combat role of supporting the civilian infrastructure of MONUC. The IAF contribution to MONUC is the largest such contribution to a UN Mission.³⁸

Winning Hearts and Minds (WHAM) Campaign

³⁸ Ibid.

Ever since its deployment in North Kivu province, 301 Brigade Group has been actively involved in WHAM activities i.e. winning the Hearts and Minds Campaign. This was primarily because it was the first UN force to be deployed in this sensitive region. Because of the Indian deployment, a large number of refugees who had fled the violence and instability in North Kivu, now began to return to their homes. Sustained interaction with the local populace enabled Indian soldiers to identify and try to ameliorate the problems they faced. In this area, the troops were in place well before any of the aid agencies and NGOs arrived, and so had a better sense of the conditions on the ground. Indian troops had one more advantage in that they were already familiar with WHAM strategies through earlier experiences of counter-insurgency operations in India itself. The following some of the important programs taken up by the 301 Indian Peacekeeping contingents:

- (i) In October 2006, the construction of a road to Kikingi village, which had been cut off from the rest of the world since the mid 1980 with local support for building the road from Mwenda to Kikingi within 15 days with the mobilisation of nearly 5,000 villagers in were mobilised to help in the construction work and FADRC troops also lent assistance;
- (ii) The construction of a bridge in Walikale territory and the repair of roads and a prison in Beni;
- (iii) Rehabilitation of 47 child soldiers;³⁹
- (iv) Vocational training to locals;
- (v) Construction and repairing of the abandoned dilapidated Sake Hydel Power Project;
- (vi) Construction of a Community Hall at Lufofo;
- (vii) Distribution of 17 wheelchairs;
- (viii) Establishment of Eagle Automotive Training School;
- (ix) Construction of Physically Challenged/Differently Abled Children as a farewell gift to the people of Rutshuru territory in North Kivu;
- (x) Youth development programmes specially to do with sports and culture;
- (xi) Awareness training on public development programmes;

³⁹ Awasthi, Mayank (2005), "No guns please, we have a future?" [Online: web] Accessed 19 September 2011, URL: <http://reliefweb.int/node/167954>

- (xii) Organisation of symposia, seminars, vocational training workshops;
- (xiii) Programmes on health and hygiene;
- (xiv) Relief and humanitarian programmes.⁴⁰

Undertaking the above programmes really benefited the local populace. The Indian 301 Infantry Brigade Group and both Indian Air Force contingents operated in areas that had witnessed extreme violence and foreign interference were able to win goodwill and trust among the local population.

The Indian peacekeepers functioned in a situation in which the Congolese government was unable to exercise stable political control. The situation on the ground in Bunia, Ituri, and Goma was grim, and the civilian population in these areas had undergone extreme suffering. Various armed factions owing allegiance to different political parties of the region were fighting for influence and control over the region. The administrative vacuum due to the absence of governmental control resulted in large-scale civil unrest and internal displacement of the population. The Congolese Army was ineffective and there was no esprit de corps or a common ethos among its rank and file. All this changed with the presence of the Indian forces in these areas.

While operating the Indian contingent experienced a number of odds like of foreign contingents, speaking different languages and having their own distinctive operating procedures in Goma, Ituri and Bunia. Maps were outdated the IAF contingent operated in difficult areas with outdated maps and often in hostile conditions. However, Indian contingent was able to deliver its best in time of need of the local populace and to MONUC's call. India's contribution in peacekeeping was duly acknowledged by the United Nations functionaries. One instance is the letter written by Jean-Marie Guehenno, Under-Secretary-General for Peacekeeping Operations, addressed to General Satyanarayana, 301 Brigade commander in North Kivu, dated 03 April 2006.⁴¹

⁴⁰ The list is taken from Nambiar supplemented by information given in various issues of the Indian Army's Participation in UN Peacekeeping Missions, Monthly Update (New Delhi).

⁴¹Nambiar, Satish (2009), *For the honour of India: A History of Indian Peacekeeping*, New Delhi: Centre for Armed Forces Historical Research, p.372.

Though the mission was mandated to operate under Chapter VII provisions of the UN Charter, implementation by forces at the operational level needed to be properly calibrated depending on prevailing conditions in every situation. Rules of engagement needed to be reviewed periodically in consultation with those operating at the ground level. This was essential in order to ensure that there was no collateral damage that would impose further suffering on an already traumatised population. Hence, the application of Chapter VII provisions is to be carefully nuanced at all times; imposing a serious burden on commanders at all levels. Whereas every effort was to be directed at ‘winning the hearts and minds’ of the locals through various projects and operating methods, it was important to understand that a single ill-considered and rash move could deal a body blow to all efforts.

In February 2007, Peter Karim, Commander of the FNI, the last remaining militia group in Ituri, made an important first step towards peace in the district. He surrendered with 170 of his troops at Dera, 60 kilometres from Kpandroma. This ended a trail of violence perpetrated by this commander. His surrender removed the final hurdle to the establishment of peace in this conflict ridden area. Some 260 Mayi-Mayi combatants also surrendered to the Armed Forces of the Democratic Republic of Congo (FARDC) based in Kamandi. After arriving at the military base on 2 March 2007, they were transported by representatives of 301 Brigade Group to the Rumangabo assembly camp for eventual integration into the regular armed forces of the DRC. The group included twenty five minors (eight were under the age of 15) who were handed over to the MONUC division for the protection of minors. The combatants were in possession of around thirty firearms and numerous other weapons, including spears. Another 50 Mayi-Mayi fighters surrendered in the last week of February 2007. All these actions indicate the possibility of peace returning to the region; a goal towards which 301 Brigade Group continues to work tirelessly.

During 2008, the Indian troops maintained a strong presence in MONUC; in fact, in November 2008, the Indian contribution was almost a quarter of the entire MONUC deployment. However, in the same month, the government of DRC is reported to have asked the UN not to send any more Indian troops to the eastern parts of the country. This followed allegations of sexual exploitation and abuse against the Indian troops in Congo, as reported

by the Office of the Internal Oversight Services (OIOS) in August 2008. Earlier, the Indian army personnel had also been accused of gold smuggling and detention of locals. As an indication that the Ministry of Defence (MoD) had taken the charges against Indian troops in the UN probe seriously, Defence Minister A.K. Antony directed the Army to investigate the allegations in a 'time-bound manner'. An internal inquiry conducted by the Army into the sexual exploitation and abuse case did not find any evidence of wrong-doing by the Indian Peacekeepers. In fact, the inquiry found irregularities in the UN investigation, including a statement by a 'minor' girl who turned out to be a 28 years old adult.

Despite the above assertion of the reinforcement General, the undeniable fact is the matching of a DNA profile of an Indian Army officer peacekeeper and the child born to a Congolese woman.⁴²

Honestly, it is very difficult to deal with and evaluate India's contribution in peacekeeping in DRC alone, no doubt, as Indian contingent was a part of the MONUC/MONUSCO. However, Indian contingent was posted at the most critical epicentres of conflict areas at the same time sensitive, the areas where one earlier survey conducted found that the people's perception of the MONUC, another Blue Helmets was most positive.⁴³ It played a crucial role in line with the mandate of the UN discussed in detail in this chapter. India was one which despatched its troop's when the UN decides to strengthen its presence in the DRC. India in a larger context played a crucial role in bringing about peace and stability in the region where it served even to the extent of sacrificing the lives of its troops.

Before we come to the end of the discussion, it is worthwhile to highlight some of the important developments which had taken place in the DRC. The most important event in the political development in the DRC is the holding of the long overdue national election. The tenure of President Kabila ended on 20 December 2016. After a delay, general elections in the DRC were finally held on 30 December 2018 to choose a successor to President Kabila and also elect 500 seats of the National Assembly and 715 Provincial Council seats. Finally, on 10 January the election commission declared Félix Tshisekedi elected as president. He

⁴² "UN probes Indian Army Officer's sexual 'misconduct' in Congo" *Times of India*, New Delhi, 15 July 2010.

⁴³ *Bureau d'Etudes de Recherches et de Consulting International (BERCI)*, Peacekeeping Operations in the Democratic Republic of Congo: the Perception of the population, 2005

was an opposition leader belonging to the Union for Democracy and Social Progress (UDSP), the oldest and the largest party of the DRC. Neighbouring countries of the DRC, the US and other powers supported Félix Tshisekedi's election 'eager to promote stability over potential chaos,' hailed the first peaceful transfer of power since DRC's independence.

On 12 January 2018, it became known that parties supporting Joseph Kabila won the majority of seats in the National Assembly, a week before the court's verdict. While Tshisekedi had won the presidential election, parties aligned with Kabila secured a majority in the National Assembly and later in the Senate during the March 2019 Senate election. Because of this, Tshisekedi's ability to implement policies or appoint a new Prime Minister became delicate as his party and allies were not in majority in both National Assembly and the Senate. Negotiations were started to form a new government while the new President was working with the former cabinet of Kabila. Later, Kabila asked Tshisekedi to appoint Albert Yuma, a Kabila ally as prime minister, but Tshisekedi refused. Finally, Sylvestre Ilunga, another ally of Kabila, a career bureaucrat who hailed from mineral rich Katanga province, the same place from where Kabila came, was appointed as Prime Minister thereby making peaceful transfer of power smooth.⁴⁴

President Tshisekedi formed a new government on 27 July 2019, choosing 65 members of the new cabinet. Out of those, 42 posts went to Common Front for Congo-aligned candidates, while 23 went to the Heading for Change Coalition (Tshisekedi's alliance). The new Ilunga government formally took office in late August 2019, seven months' after Tshisekedi's inauguration as president after reaching a mutually acceptable compromise. The smooth peaceful transfer of power was a rare achievement in its history. The new president pardoned hundreds of prisoners to create a more congenial peaceful political environment.⁴⁵

Regarding peacekeeping, India has been playing a significant role in it in the DRC. Before we come to DRC, it is worthwhile to point out that India is the largest contributor of UN peacekeeping troops cumulatively. It has provided more than 200,000 troops since 1950 and

⁴⁴ "2018 Democratic Republic of the Congo general election" in https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/2018_Democratic_Republic_of_the_Congo_general_election, accessed 10 May 2020

⁴⁵ DRC announces new government 7 months after president inaugurated: Coalition government under President Felix Tshisekedi dominated by former leader Joseph Kabila's FCC movement. See <https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2019/08/dr-congo-announces-gov-7-months-presidentinaugurated-190826061019033.html>, accessed 11 May 2020

sacrificed 163 personnel (Out of a world total of 3802 between 1948- 2018). It is the fourth largest troop contributor with 6,319 after Ethiopia (7,499), Rwanda (6546) and Bangladesh (6487) worldwide as of 30 April 2019⁴⁶. India's Centre for United Nations Peacekeeping located in New Delhi runs courses on capacity building in peacekeeping. It conducted its third course in association with the United States for African partners (UNPCAP) in July 2018 in which a total of 40 participants attended. MEA writes, "For the first time courses were offered in French for the benefit of Francophone African countries."⁴⁷

Regarding MONUSCO, it is the second largest contributor of peacekeepers with 1909 after Pakistan (1975). The third, fourth and fifth largest contributors are Bangladesh (1677), South Africa (1060) and Indonesia (1034) as of October 2020. At the same time, it is the fourth largest police contributor with 183 personnel after Egypt (320) Senegal (294), Bangladesh (183). Next to India comes Niger (27).⁴⁸ India is the First ever formed female police unit for the UN in Liberia beginning in July 2007.

One interesting feature in UN peacekeeping is the induction of women armed peacekeepers in recent years. Increasing deployment of female peacekeepers is believed to contribute to achieving sustainable peace and the improved well-being of women and girls in conflict areas. UN Security Council Resolution 1925 adopted unanimously on 28 May 2010 urged equal participation of women at all sectors, including the military. In 1993, women made up 1 per cent of the deployed uniformed personnel. In 2019, out of 95,000 peacekeepers, women contributed 4.1 per cent. Of the 98,000 peacekeepers currently deployed in 13 missions around the world, 6 per cent are women uniformed military, police justice, as correctional personnel. In society where there is gender inequality they are the role models to young girls. It is truer in the case of African countries. Moreover, female military bring additional advantage in screening civilians, conducting house searches in areas where it is not culturally appropriate to enter private spaces.⁴⁹ Local population in host countries feel more

⁴⁶ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_countries_by_number_of_UN_peacekeepers , accessed 10 September 2020. Military personnel include contingent troops, experts on mission and staff officers.

⁴⁷ MEA, 2018-19, p.224.

⁴⁸ MONUSCO Fact Sheet, <https://peacekeeping.un.org/en/mission/> monusco, accessed 6 December 2020.

⁴⁹ "Female Military: It is essential that we increase the representation of female military in UN peacekeeping operations" in <https://peacekeeping.un.org/en/female-military/>, accessed 15 September 2020.

comfortable when they see military troops that include women alongside men.⁵⁰ For India, twenty-two women Indian peacekeepers led by Captain Preeti Sharma joined the Indian contingent on 5 June 2019 in the DRC.⁵¹ The Indian peacekeepers are deployed in the eastern part of the country where most of the violent clashes take place. One information says that Indian contingent governs an area approximately 5 lakhs sq. kms, covering a vast area almost a quarter of the country.⁵² What is worth mentioning is that the area where Indian contingent is serving is the home of more than 30 groups operating out of a total of 121 armed groups in the DRC. In one of the most successful latest stories, the Indian peacekeepers' efforts led to the surrender of 39 cadres including Second-in-Command of Mai Mai Kitete armed group, a prominent Armed Group in North Kivu, DR Congo in July 2020 (See the photograph below). Lastly, Indian peacekeepers saved the lives of a number of child soldiers for instance, 47 of them were rehabilitated. Further, protection of civilians is the key mandate of the mission," the Indian Army said.⁵³

⁵⁰ "Women in Peacekeeping: A Key to Peace, 29 May International Day of UN Peacekeepers" <https://peacekeeping.un.org/en/women-peacekeeping#:~:text=In%201993%2C%20women%20made%20up,units%20in%20UN%20Peacekeeping%20missions,15%20September%202020.> See also <http://ddnews.gov.in/international/congo-indian-peacekeepers-garner-appreciationprofessionalism#:~:text=India%20is%20the%20second%20largest,deployed%20as%20of%20March%202020>, accessed 21 August 2020

⁵¹ 25 "Indian women peacekeepers begin UN mission in Congo" in <https://www.financialexpress.com/defence/indian-womenpeacekeepers-begin-un-mission-in-congo/1616923/>, accessed 15 September 2020.

⁵² "Indian peacekeepers in Congo garner appreciation for their professionalism" in https://www.business-standard.com/article/ti-stories/indian-peacekeepers-in-congo-garner-appreciationfor-their-professionalism-119061100228_1.html, accessed 15 September 2020.

⁵³ Indian peacekeepers' efforts result in surrender of 39 cadre of armed groups in DR Congo. <https://www.indiatvnews.com/news/world/indian-peacekeepers-efforts-led-in-surrenderof-39-cadre-of-prominent-armed-group-in-congo-636035>, accessed 15 September 2020. See also <https://www.outlookindia.com/newscroll/indian-peacekeepers-efforts-result-in-surrenderof-39-cadre-of-armed-group-in-dr-congo/1899846>, accessed 15 September 2020. September 2020

Image Source: TWITTER/@ADGPI

To end, it is aimed that all UN peacekeepers are likely to withdraw completely by the end of 2024.⁵⁴

⁵⁴ <https://www.aljazeera.com/news/2024/1/13/un-says-all-peacekeepers-will-leave-dr-congo-by-end-of-2024>,

Accessed 26 March 2024.

Received: 12 March 2024

Revised: 23 March 2024

Final Accepted: 6 April 2024

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10936060>